

Stilbenoids and flavonoids from the orchids *Coelogyne uniflora*, *Ione paleacea* and *Acrochoene punctata*

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The orchid *Coelogyne uniflora* afforded earlier a steroidal ester, uniflorin. Further investigation of this orchid has now resulted in the isolation of two new phenanthropyrone derivatives, unifloranthrone and uniflorinanthrone, besides flavidin (1a), flavidin (1c), isoflavinidin (1d) and oxoflavinidin (1e). The structures of unifloranthrone and uniflorinanthrone were established as 2,7-dihydroxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one (2a) and 2,7-dimethoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one (2c), respectively, from spectral and chemical evidence. Chemical investigation of the orchid *Ione paleacea* yielded two flavanone derivatives, 5,7-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (3a) and 5,7-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-2-(4'-hydroxyphenyl)-2,3-dihydro-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (3c), besides the known stilbenoids, 3-hydroxy-5-methoxybibenzyl (4a), batatasin-III (4c) and gigantol (4e). The orchid *Acrochoene punctata* afforded two known bibenzyl derivatives, viz. 3,4'-dihydroxy-5-methoxybibenzyl (4f) and 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,5-dimethoxybibenzyl (4g). Additional NMR spectral evidence was provided for further confirmation of the structures of 3a, 3c, 4a and 4g.

We reported earlier the isolation of a fairly large number of compounds from a series of Indian orchids. These compounds encompass a wide variety of stilbenoids, viz. stilbene¹, bibenzyls^{2,3}, phenanthrenes⁴ and 9,10-dihydrophenanthrenes^{5,6} and their dimers⁷⁻⁹, phenanthropyranes and pyrones^{10,11} and their 9,10-dihydroderivatives¹²⁻¹⁴, fluorenonones¹⁵, a few other polyphenolics^{16,17}, several triterpenoids¹⁸ and steroids¹⁹ of biogenetic importance and some simple aromatic compounds²⁰. As part of this general programme of research, we have chemically investigated three orchids, viz. *Coelogyne uniflora*, *Ione paleacea* and *Acrochoene punctata*. The orchid *C. uniflora* afforded earlier a steroidal ester, uniflorin¹⁹. Further investigation of this orchid has now resulted in the isolation of two new phenanthropyrone derivatives, designated unifloranthrone and uniflorinanthrone, besides the known stilbenoids, flavidin (1a)²¹, flavidin (1c)²², isoflavinidin (1d)²³ and oxoflavinidin (1e)²⁴. The structures of unifloranthrone and uniflorinanthrone were established as 2,7-dihydroxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one (2a) and 2,7-dimethoxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one (2c), respectively, from spectral and chemical evidence. The orchid *I. paleacea* afforded two flavanone derivatives, 5,7-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (3a)²⁵⁻²⁸ and 5,7-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-2-(4'-hydroxyphenyl)-2,3-dihydro-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (3c)²⁵⁻²⁸, besides the known bibenzyl derivatives, 3-hydroxy-5-methoxybibenzyl (4a)^{29,30}, batatasin-III (4c)³¹ and gigantol (4e)³². From the orchid *A. punctata* were isolated two known bibenzyl derivatives, 3,4'-dihydroxy-5-methoxy-

xybibenzyl (4f)^{3,33,34} and 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,5-dimethoxybibenzyl (4g)³⁵⁻³⁷. While the known compounds 1a, 1c, 1d, 1e, 4c, 4e and 4f were identified by direct comparison with authentic samples, compounds 3a, 3c, 4a and 4g were characterized by independent spectral analysis and their structures were further confirmed by additional spectroscopical evidence.

Results and Discussion

Both unifloranthrone (2a), C₁₅H₈O₄ ([M]⁺ at *m/z* 252) and uniflorinanthrone (2c), C₁₇H₁₂O₄ ([M]⁺ at *m/z* 280) showed UV absorptions [2a : λ_{max} 226 and 253.5 nm (log ε 4.18 and 4.00) : 2c : 203, 221.5, 259.5 and 384.5 nm (3.87, 3.85, 4.01 and 3.19)] which are strikingly similar to those of the phenanthropyrone derivatives like flaccidin (2d)³⁸ and isoflaccidin (2e)³⁹.

Both 2a and 2c were shown to contain a δ-lactone function as indicated by their IR spectra (2a : ν_{max} 1705; 2c : 1733 cm⁻¹). But while the IR spectrum of 2a exhibited a strong band at 3310 cm⁻¹ for phenolic hydroxyl function(s), that of 2c is devoid of any such band. The phenolic nature of 2a was also indicated by its characteristic colour reactions [FeCl₃ : violet; phosphomolybdic acid : deep blue]. The presence of two phenolic hydroxyl groups in 2a was confirmed by the formation of its diacetyl derivative 2b, C₁₉H₁₂O₆ ([M]⁺ at *m/z* 336), with Ac₂O and pyridine.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of 2a showed, as expected, signals for two phenolic hydroxyl protons at δ 7.46 and 7.60 (each 1H, br s, disappeared on deuterium exchange) which were replaced by the signals at δ 4.03 and 4.04 (each 3H, s) for two aromatic methoxyl groups in the ¹H NMR

- 1a: R¹=R²=R³=R⁴=H
 1b: R¹=R⁴=Ac, R²=R³=H
 1c: R¹=Me, R²=R³=R⁴=H
 1d: R¹=R²=R³=H, R⁴=Me
 1e: R¹=R⁴=H, R²=R³=O
 1f: R¹=R⁴=Ac, R²=R³=O
 1g: R¹=R⁴=Me, R²=R³=H
 1h: R¹=R⁴=Me, R²=R³=O

- 2a: R¹=R²=R³=H, R⁴=O
 2b: R¹=R²=Ac, R³=H, R⁴=O
 2c: R¹=R²=Me, R³=H, R⁴=O
 2d: R¹=Me, R²=OH, R³=O, R⁴=H
 2e: R¹=R²=H, R³=OMe, R⁴=O
 2f: R¹=Ac, R²=OMe, R³=O, R⁴=Me
 2g: R¹=Me, R²=OAc, R³=O, R⁴=Ac
 2h: R¹=R²=Me, R³=OMe, R⁴=O

- 3a: R¹=R²=H
 3b: R¹=H, R²=Ac
 3c: R¹=OH, R²=H
 3d: R¹=OAc, R²=Ac

- 4a: R¹=R²=R³=R⁴=H, R⁵=Me
 4b: R¹=Ac, R²=R³=R⁴=H, R⁵=Me
 4c: R¹=R²=R³=H, R⁴=Me, R⁵=OH
 4d: R¹=Ac, R²=R³=H, R⁴=Me, R⁵=OAc
 4e: R¹=R²=H, R³=Me, R⁴=OMe, R⁵=OH
 4f: R¹=R²=R³=H, R⁴=Me, R⁵=OH
 4g: R¹=R²=Me, R³=R⁴=OH, R⁵=H
 4h: R¹=R²=Me, R³=R⁴=OAc, R⁵=H
 4i: R¹=R²=Me, R³=R⁴=OH, R⁵=OMe
 4j: R¹=R²=Me, R³=OH, R⁴=H, R⁵=OMe
 4k: R¹=R²=Me, R³=R⁴=OH, R⁵=H
 4l: R¹=R²=Me, R³=R⁴=OAc, R⁵=H
 4m: R¹=R²=R³=R⁴=H, R⁵=OH

spectrum of **2c**. The spectra of both **2a** and **2c** were characterized by the appearance of signals for six aromatic protons [**2a**: δ 7.03, 7.18, 7.71 and 7.81 (each 1H, ill-res. *meta*-coupled doublet) and 7.77 (2H, s); **2c**: δ 8.21 and 7.89 (each 1H, d, *J* 9.33 Hz), 8.18 and 7.76 (each 1H, d, *J* 2.40 Hz) and 7.36 (2H, ill-res. br signal)]. The signal at δ 7.77 of **2a** and those at δ 8.21 and 7.89 of **2c** are typical of H-9 and H-10 of a phenanthropyrone derivative^{38,39}. The remaining four aromatic proton signals of **2a** at δ 7.03, 7.18, 7.71 and 7.81 may be attributed to H-8, H-6, H-1 and H-3, respectively, of a 2,7-dihydroxyphenanthropyrene. Similarly, the remaining four aromatic proton signals at δ 7.76, 8.18 and 7.36 of **2c** may be assigned to H-1, H-3 and H-6 and H-8, respectively, of the corresponding 2,7-dimethoxyphenanthropyrene analogue. This would suggest that while unifloranthrone may be represented as 2,7-dihydroxy-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran-5-one (**2a**), uniflorinanthrone (**2c**) is the corresponding dimethyl ether derivative of **2a**. Although according to systematic nomenclature **2a** and **2c** are named as stated above, the phenanthrene numbering system has been followed in this paper for convenience of spectral comparison. The placement of the two phenolic hydroxyl groups in **2a** at C-2 and C-7 was also supported by the downfield shifts of its H-6, H-8, H-3 and H-1 by 0.34, 0.41, 0.53 and 0.32 ppm, respectively, in the ¹H NMR spectrum of its diacetyl derivative **2b**.

The above contention was confirmed by the conversion of **2a** to **2c** by the action of CH₂N₂.

The structures of **2a** and **2c** were also supported by the

¹³C NMR spectral data of **2b** (more soluble in CDCl₃ than **2a** itself) and **2c** (Table 1). The degree of protonation of each carbon atom of **2b** and **2c** (and those of all other compounds reported in this paper) was established by DEPT experiments and the carbon resonances of the compounds were assigned by comparison with the δ_C values of structurally similar compounds, viz. flaccidin diacetate (**2g**)³⁸, agrostophylloxin (**2h**)¹¹ and agrostophyllone acetate (**2f**)¹¹. The presence of a δ -lactone function in both unifloranthrone diacetate (**2b**) and uniflorinanthrone (**2c**) as part of a phenanthropyrene skeletal structure was confirmed by the characteristic carbonyl carbon resonances at δ_C 160.2 and 158.0, respectively. The carbon resonances of **2b** at δ_C 127.6 and 126.7 and those of **2c** at δ_C 127.8 and 126.7 are again typical of C-9 and C-10 of a phenanthrene derivative. The virtually identical δ_C values of C-4b, C-5, C-6, C-7, C-8 and C-8a of unifloranthrone diacetate (**2b**) and flaccidin diacetate (**2g**) (Table 1) affirmed the structural identity of their ring-C of a phenanthropyrene derivative bearing an acetoxy group at C-7. Similarly, the essentially identical chemical shifts of the above carbon atoms of uniflorinanthrone (**2c**), agrostophyllone acetate (**2f**) and agrostophylloxin (**2h**) (Table 1) confirmed the structural identity of their ring-C of a phenanthropyrene derivative having a methoxyl function at C-7. The chemical shifts of the remaining carbon atoms of **2b** and **2c** are also consistent with their assigned structures.

Table 1. ¹³C NMR spectral data of **2b**, **2c**, **2g**, **2f** and **2h**

C ^{††}	Chemical shifts (δ ppm)				
	2b [†]	2c [†]	2f [†]	2g [†]	2h [†]
1	125.4	121.9	127.4	115.0	115.3
2	150.4 ^a	160.0	143.6 ^f	150.2 ^h	151.2 ^j
3	122.6	119.0	144.1 ^f	151.6 ^h	152.7 ^j
4	118.0	117.0	108.8	113.0	109.3
4a	125.3	123.9	124.9	126.8	123.0
4b	127.5	125.1	125.1	128.1	125.5
5	150.6 ^a	152.0	151.5	151.8 ^h	152.8 ^j
6	108.2	101.8	102.0	107.4	101.8
7	149.6	160.0	160.3	149.8	159.5
8	115.0	105.0	104.8	114.7	104.4
8a	131.2 ^b	131.7 ^d	132.3	131.9	131.4
9	127.6 ^c	127.8 ^e	126.4 ^g	126.9 ⁱ	126.4 ^k
10	126.7 ^c	126.7 ^e	126.3 ^g	126.5 ⁱ	125.9 ^k
10a	130.7 ^b	130.7 ^e	125.1	130.6	124.3
ArO-COAr	160.2	158.0	158.2	157.1	158.1
OMe	-	55.0	55.9	55.6	55.8
		56.0	62.9	-	56.2
					62.0
OAc	169.0	-	169.3	169.0	
	169.1		20.7	169.2	
	21.0			20.9	
	21.1			21.2	

[†]Spectra were run in CDCl₃ and the chemical shifts were measured with $\delta_{TMS} = \delta_{CDCl_3} + 76.9$ ppm.

^{††}For convenience of spectral comparison, the phenanthrene numbering system of carbon atoms has been followed.

^{a-k}Values are interchangeable within each column.

The structures of unifloranthrone (**2a**) and uniflorinanthrone (**2c**) were finally confirmed by the following chemical evidence. Dehydrogenation of both flavidin diacetate (**1b**) and oxoflavin diacetate (**1f**) with DDQ in dry benzene afforded the same unifloranthrone diacetate (**2b**) which on acid hydrolysis finally gave unifloranthrone (**2a**). Similar dehydrogenation of flavidin dimethyl ether (**1g**) and oxoflavin dimethyl ether (**1h**) with DDQ, as expected, also afforded uniflorinanthrone (**2c**).

Unifloranthrone (**2a**) and uniflorinanthrone (**2c**) are thus two new additions to the growing list of naturally occurring phenanthropyron derivatives.

The UV, IR and the ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectral data of the two flavanone derivatives isolated from the orchid *I. paleacea* compared excellently with those reported^{25–28} for **3a** and **3c** suggesting their structural identity, although direct comparison could not be made due to nonavailability of authentic samples. We report in this paper some additional spectroscopical evidence, viz. the ^{13}C NMR spectral data of the diacetyl derivative of **3a** (**3b**) and those of the triacetyl derivative of **3c** (**3d**) (Table 2). Comparison of the carbon resonances of **3b** and **3d** with those of the original phenolic compounds **3a** and **3c** (also recorded by us independently) not only confirmed the reported assignments of the δ_c values of **3a** and **3c** but also revealed some diagnostic ^{13}C NMR spectral evidence for the presence of a 5-hydroxyflavanone moiety in **3a** and **3c**. Thus, the lowfield shifts of the flavanone carbonyl carbons of **3a** and **3c** by 7.4 and 7.9 ppm, respectively, compared with those of the corresponding carbon atom of **3b** and **3d** may be attributed to the reduced carbonyl character of the flavanone carbonyl group caused primarily by the strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding between the above carbonyl function with the hydroxyl group at C-5 and partly by the electron-donating effects of the above hydroxyl group and that at C-7. This was also supported by the upfield shifts of C-3 of **3a** and **3c** by 1.7 and 3.0 ppm, respectively, compared with those of the corresponding carbon atom of their respective acetyl derivatives **3b** and **3d**. The virtually unchanged δ_c values of C-9 of **3a** and **3c** in the spectra of their respective acetyl derivatives **3b** and **3d** and the relatively lowfield resonances (δ_c 59.9–61.4) of the methoxyl carbons of **3a**, **3b**, **3c** and **3d** justified the placement of the lone methoxyl group at C-6 flanked by hydroxyl functions at C-5 and C-7 in **3a** and **3c** and acetoxy functions at the same positions in **3b** and **3d**. The downfield shifts of C-6, C-8 and C-10 of **3b** and **3d** by 11.0 and 10.7, 15.3 and 14.9 and 9.3 and 10.5 ppm, respectively, compared with the corresponding carbon atoms of **3a** and **3c** confirmed the placement of the two phenolic hydroxyl functions of **3a** at C-5 and C-7, and two of the three such functions of **3c** at the same positions. The placement of the remaining hydroxyl group of **3c** at C-4' was confirmed by the downfield shifts of C-1' and C-3'

(and C-5') of **3d** by 6.6 and 6.7 ppm, respectively, compared with the corresponding carbon atoms of **3c**, the δ_c values of C-2' (and C-6') of **3c** remaining practically unchanged in the spectrum of **3d**. The δ_c values of C-1', C-2' (C-6'), C-3' (C-5') and C-4' of **3a** corresponded to an unsubstituted phenyl ring at C-2. This was further confirmed by the virtually identical δ_c values of these carbon atoms of both **3a** and **3b**.

Table 2. ^{13}C NMR spectral data of **3a-d**

C	Chemical shifts (δ ppm)			
	3a [†]	3b ^{††}	3c [†]	3d ^{††}
2	79.1	79.3	78.4	78.9
3	43.2	44.9	42.1	45.1
4	196.4	189.0	196.8	188.9
5	154.3	143.6	155.0	143.8
6	128.4	139.4	129.0	139.7
7	158.4	149.8	159.4	150.0
8	94.6	109.9	95.1	110.0
9	157.6	157.7	157.6	157.8
10	103.0	112.3	102.0	112.5
1'	138.4	138.0	129.0	135.6
2'	126.0	125.8	127.9	127.1
3'	128.7	128.5	115.2	121.9
4'	128.4	128.5	157.9	151.0
5'	128.7	128.5	115.2	121.9
6'	126.0	125.8	127.9	127.1
OMe	60.8	61.3	59.9	61.4
OAc	–	168.5	–	168.9
		167.5		168.6
		20.6		167.6
		20.3		20.9
				20.7
				20.4

[†]Spectra were run in d_6 -DMSO and the chemical shifts were measured with $\delta_{\text{TMS}} = \delta_{d_6\text{-DMSO}} + 39.7$ ppm.

^{††}Spectra were run in CDCl_3 and the chemical shifts were measured with $\delta_{\text{TMS}} = \delta_{\text{CDCl}_3} + 76.9$ ppm.

The equatorial orientations of the phenyl group at C-2 in **3a** and **3b** and the 4-hydroxyphenyl group in **3c** and 4-acetoxyphenyl substituent at the same position in **3d** were confirmed by the splitting patterns of the signals for H-2 and H₂-3 of **3a**, **3b**, **3c** and **3d** constituting typical ABX system. H-2 of these compounds representing the X part of the ABX system appeared in the region δ 5.33–5.49 as double doublets having J values in the region of 13.0–13.68 and 2.66–3.10 Hz corresponding to coupling between H-2 (ax) and H-3 (ax) and H-2 (ax) and H-3 (equat), respectively. The H-3 (equat) and H-3 (ax) constituting the AB part resonated in the region δ 2.66–3.10 having J values [$J_{\text{H-3(ax)}-\text{H-3(equat)}}$] about 17 Hz. This would suggest that H-2 of all the above compounds must be axial in nature and hence the phenyl substituent at C-2 in each of these compounds must be equatorially oriented.

The isolation of **3a** and **3c** represents the second report of the occurrence of flavanone derivatives in an Orchidaceae plant, the first report being that of pinobanksin⁴⁰ from the orchid *Bulbophyllum odoratissimum*⁴¹.

The bibenzyl derivative **4a** isolated from the orchid *I. paleacea* was first reported²⁹, without any spectral evidence, to occur in the heartwood of *Pinus albicaulis*. It was also later isolated³⁰ from *Dioscorea batatas* inoculated with *Pseudomonas cichorii*. The other bibenzyl derivative **4g** obtained from the orchid *A. punctata* was first reported from *Combretum psidiodes*^{35,36} and later from *C. apiculatum*³⁷. The UV, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data of **4a** and **4g** are virtually identical with those reported earlier^{30,35,36} for these compounds and the structures of these compounds were based mainly on the above spectral data. Thus, the ¹H NMR spectrum of **4a** showed signals for an aromatic methoxyl and a phenolic hydroxyl function and eight aromatic protons, while that of **4g** exhibited signals for two aromatic methoxyl, two phenolic hydroxyl groups and six aromatic protons. The spectra of both **4a** and **4g** were characterized by the appearance of a four-proton signal at *ca* δ 2.75–2.85 which is typical of the four benzylic protons of a bibenzyl derivative. The presence of a single phenolic hydroxyl group in **4a** and two such functions in **4g** was confirmed by the formation of their respective acetyl derivatives **4b** and **4h** with Ac₂O and pyridine.

The bibenzyl nature of **4a** and **4g** and the distribution of their functional groups in the two phenyl rings of the compounds were confirmed by their mass spectral fragmentations. Thus, the appearance of two intense peaks at *m/z* 91 and 137 in the mass spectrum of **4a** and those at *m/z* 107

and 167 in the spectrum of **4g** established that while **4a** was composed of an unsubstituted benzyl moiety and another benzyl residue containing a methoxyl and a hydroxyl group, **4g** was also made up of two benzyl units, one of which contained a hydroxyl and two methoxyl groups, the other bearing a single hydroxyl function.

The structures of **4a** and **4g** have now been further confirmed including the relative positions of their functional groups by the ¹³C NMR spectral data of the compounds and their acetyl derivatives **4b** and **4h** (Table 3). The chemical shifts of the carbon atoms of **4a**, **4b**, **4g** and **4h** were assigned by comparison with the δ_c values of structurally related compounds. Thus, the δ_c values of C- α' , C-1, C-2, C-3, C-4, C-5 and C-6 of **4a** are almost identical with those of the corresponding carbon atoms of batatasin-III (**4c**)³¹ and gigantol (**4e**)³², confirming the presence of a 3-hydroxy-5-methoxybenzyl moiety in **4a**. This was further confirmed by the essentially similar δ_c values of the above carbon atoms of **4b** and batatasin-III diacetate (**4d**) containing a 3-acetoxy-5-methoxybenzyl unit. The unsubstituted nature of the other benzyl moiety of both **4a** and **4b** was confirmed by the virtual identity of the δ_c values of C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5' and C-6' of both the compounds with those of the aromatic carbon atoms of *n*-propylbenzene⁴². Now, coming to the other bibenzyl derivative **4g**, it has been observed that the δ_c values of C- α' , C-1, C-2, C-3, C-4, C-5 and C-6 of **4g** are virtually identical with those of the corresponding

Table 3. ¹³C NMR spectral data of **4a-m**

C	Chemical shifts (δ ppm)												
	4a [†]	4b [†]	4c [†]	4d [†]	4e [†]	4g ^{††}	4h [†]	4i [†]	4j [†]	4k [†]	4l [†]	4m [†]	4n [†]
1	144.3	144.0	145.0	143.7	144.5	132.8 ^f	138.9 ^h	132.8 ⁱ	133.4	132.8 ^o	139.7	145.2	145.0
2	108.0	113.8	108.3	113.7	108.1	106.3	105.5	105.2	105.0	105.4	105.0	108.0	107.7
3	156.5	151.6	158.2	151.5	156.7	147.9	152.0	146.8 ^k	147.0	146.8	151.7	159.5	157.9
4	99.1	105.0	99.9	105.2	99.2	132.7 ^f	131.5	133.5	132.4 ^m	132.9 ^o	130.0	98.9	100.7
5	160.8	160.3	161.9	160.2	160.9	147.9	152.0	146.8 ^k	147.0	146.8	151.7	161.4	157.9
6	106.6	111.9	106.3	111.8	106.9	106.3	105.5	105.2	105.0	105.4	105.0	106.7	107.7
1'	141.6	141.3	144.3	143.0	133.7	133.0	139.7 ^h	132.7 ⁱ	132.6 ^m	143.3	143.1	133.8	133.2
2'	128.2	128.2	116.2	121.3	114.3	129.7	129.3	111.2	129.3	115.2	121.6	129.4	129.9
3'	128.3	128.3	159.2	150.7	146.3	115.3	121.3	146.1 ^k	113.6	155.9	150.6	115.1	115.8
4'	125.8	125.9	113.6	119.1	143.8	155.8	149.1	143.7	157.9	112.9	119.1	154.2	154.8
5'	128.3	128.3	130.0	129.1	111.4	115.3	121.3	114.1	113.6	129.2	129.1	115.1	115.8
6'	128.2	128.2	120.4	125.8	121.0	129.7	129.3	121.0	129.3	120.5	125.9	129.4	129.9
α	37.7 ^a	37.6 ^b	37.3 ^c	37.3 ^d	38.1 ^e	38.6 ^e	38.2 ⁱ	38.3 ^j	38.3 ⁿ	37.7 ^p	38.8 ^q	38.1 ^r	38.8 ^s
α'	37.3 ^a	37.2 ^b	36.9 ^c	37.0 ^d	37.1 ^e	37.5 ^e	37.0 ⁱ	37.8 ^j	37.2 ⁿ	36.7 ^p	37.5 ^q	36.6 ^r	37.3 ^s
OMe	55.1	55.2	55.6	55.2	55.2	56.0	56.1	55.7	55.2	56.2	55.9	55.2	—
				55.9				55.1	56.2				
OAc	—	169.0	—	169.3	—	—	168.4	—	—	—	168.8	—	—
		21.0	—	21.0	—	—	20.8	—	—	—	168.2	—	—
							20.2	—	—	—	20.9	—	—
											20.0	—	—

[†]The spectra were run in CDCl₃ and the chemical shifts were measured with $\delta_{TMS} = \delta_{CDCl_3} + 76.9$ ppm.

^{††}The spectrum was run in acetone-*d*₆ and the chemical shifts were measured with $\delta_{TMS} = \delta_{acetone-d_6} + 29.6$ ppm.

^{a-s}Values are interchangeable within each column.

carbon atoms of moscatilin (**4i**)⁴³, amoenin (**4j**)³ and aloifol-I (**4k**)⁴⁴ confirming the presence of a 4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxybenzyl moiety in **4g**. This was also corroborated by the fact that the δ_c values of the above carbon atoms of **4h** (the diacetyl derivative of **4g**) are also essentially similar to those of the corresponding carbon atoms of aloifol-I diacetate (**4l**)². Again, the δ_c values of C- α , C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5' and C-6' of **4g** are almost identical with the corresponding carbon atoms of **4f**³ and dihydroresveratrol (**4m**)⁴⁵ having a 4-hydroxybenzyl moiety. The structure of **4g** is thus established as 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,5-dimethoxybibenzyl.

In view of the fact that several polyoxygenated bibenzyl derivatives are reported to exhibit strong antimitotic property⁴⁶, while others are known to act as potent endogenous plant growth regulators⁴⁷, it would be interesting to study **4a**, **4g** and other bibenzyl derivatives isolated from *I. paleacea* and *A. punctata* for similar biological activities.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Column chromatography was done on silica gel (100–200 mesh) and TLC on silica gel G. UV spectra were recorded in 95% aldehyde-free EtOH and IR spectra on KBr discs. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were run at 300 and 75 MHz, respectively, in CDCl₃ using TMS as an internal standard. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ (ppm). Mass spectra were recorded at 70 eV using a direct inlet system. All analytical samples were routinely dried over P₂O₅ for 24 h *in vacuo* and were tested for purity by TLC and MS. Petrol used had b.p. 60–80°.

Isolation of unifloranthrone (2a), uniflorinanthrone (2c), flavidin (1a), flavidin (1c), isoflavinidin (1d) and oxoflavinidin (1e) from Coelogyne uniflora; the flavanones 3a and 3c and the bibenzyl derivatives 4a, 4c and 4e from Ione paleacea; the bibenzyls 4f and 4g from Acrochoene punctata : Air-dried powdered whole plants of *C. uniflora* (3 kg), *I. paleacea* (2.5 kg) and *A. punctata* (2 kg) were separately kept soaked with 9, 7 and 6 L of MeOH, respectively, for 2 weeks. The MeOH extract in each case was concentrated to ca 100 ml, diluted with H₂O (500 ml) and exhaustively extracted with Et₂O. The Et₂O extracts were separately fractionated into acidic and nonacidic fractions with 2 M NaOH. The aq. alkaline solution in each case was acidified in the cold with conc. HCl and the liberated solids were extracted with Et₂O, washed with H₂O, dried and the solvent removed. The Et₂O extract in each case after removal of the acidic compounds, was similarly washed with H₂O, dried and the solvent removed. The acidic and neutral fractions thus obtained from all the three orchids were separately chromatographed.

Chromatography of the acidic fraction obtained from C. uniflora : The petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate afforded a mixture of flavidin (**1a**), flavidin (**1c**) and isoflavinidin

(**1d**). Rechromatography of this mixture finally gave pure **1a** (0.05 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 210°, **1c** (0.04 g), crystallized from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 168°, and **1d** (0.03 g), also crystallized from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 120°. Washing the main column with petrol-EtOAc (7 : 1) gave oxoflavinidin (**1e**; 0.04 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 255°. Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (1 : 1) afforded unifloranthrone (**2a**; 0.06 g), amorph. powder (Found : C, 71.37; H, 3.10. C₁₅H₈O₄ requires : C, 71.41; H, 3.19%); $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}-0.1M \text{ NaOH}}$ 226 and 268 nm (log ϵ 4.17 and 3.99); ν_{\max} 3310 (OH), 1705 (lactone C=O), 1625, 1585, 1505, 865, 835, 745, 685 and 662 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); *m/z* (rel. int.) 252 [M⁺] (100), 224 (4), 223 (11), 207 (7), 196 (4), 195 (6), 168 (8), 167 (8) and 139 (15). Acetylation of **2a** with Ac₂O and pyridine in the usual manner gave **2b**, crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 230° (Found : C, 67.71; H, 3.51; C₁₉H₁₂O₆ requires : C, 67.83; H, 3.59%); λ_{\max} 217, 237 (sh), 253, 355.5 and 373.5 nm (log ϵ 4.06, 4.04, 4.16, 3.21 and 3.28); ν_{\max} 1210 and 1762 (OAc), 1735 (lactone C=O), 1632, 1595, 845, 755 and 690 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR δ 2.41 and 2.42 (each 3H, s, 2 × OAc), 7.37 (1H, d, *J* 1.16 Hz, H-8), 7.59 (1H, d, *J* 1.6 Hz, H-6), 7.87 (2H, s, H-9 and H-10), 8.03 (1H, d, *J* 1.3 Hz, H-1) and 8.34 (1H, d, *J* 1.3 Hz, H-3); *m/z* (rel. int.) 336 [M⁺] (19), 294 (33), 252 (100), 224 (5), 223 (13), 207 (9), 196 (5), 195 (8), 168 (10), 167 (10) and 139 (17).

Chromatography of the neutral fraction obtained from C. uniflora : The petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) eluate gave uniflorin (0.075 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 215°. Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (30 : 1) afforded pure uniflorinanthrone (**2c**) as a semisolid mass (Found : C, 72.79; H, 4.25. C₁₇H₁₂O₄ requires : C, 72.85; H, 4.32%); ν_{\max} 1730 (δ -lactone), 1615, 1463, 895, 839, 804 and 749 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus).

Methylation of unifloranthrone (2a) with CH₂N₂ : To a solution of unifloranthrone (0.02 g) in MeOH (15 ml) was added an excess of CH₂N₂ in Et₂O and the reaction mixture was kept overnight in an ice-bath. MeOH was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue extracted with Et₂O, washed with dilute NaOH and then H₂O, dried and the solvent removed. The residue was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (30 : 1) eluate afforded uniflorinanthrone (**2c**; 0.015 g) as a semisolid mass.

Conversion of flavidin diacetate (1b) and oxoflavinidin diacetate (1f) to unifloranthrone diacetate (2b) by dehydrogenation with DDQ and the acid hydrolysis of 2b to 2a : To solutions of **1b** (0.05 g) in dry C₆H₆ (25 ml) and **1f** (0.05 g) in the same solvent (25 ml) were added 0.085 and 0.06 g of DDQ, respectively. The resultant mixtures were separately heated under reflux for 25 and 18 h, respectively. The solvent in each case was removed under reduced pres-

sure to give a solid which was extracted with Et₂O, washed 3 times with 2 M aq. NaOH and then with H₂O, dried and the solvent removed. The residues were separately chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (3 : 1) eluate in the chromatography of the product obtained from **1b** gave **2b** (0.038 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 230°. Similar chromatography of the product obtained from **1f** also gave **2b** (0.042 g) in the same eluate.

To a solution of **2b** (0.03 g) in MeOH (20 ml) was added 2 M aq. HCl (5 ml) and the mixture was heated under reflux for 5 h. MeOH was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue extracted with Et₂O, washed with H₂O, dried and the solvent removed. The residue was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (1 : 1) eluate gave pure **2a** (0.025 g) as an amorph. powder.

Conversion of flavidin dimethyl ether (1g) and oxoflavin dimethyl ether (1h) to uniflorinanthrone (2c) by dehydrogenation with DDQ: To solutions of **1g** (0.04 g) in dry C₆H₆ (20 ml) and **1h** (0.04 g) in the same solvent (20 ml) were added 0.07 and 0.05 g of DDQ, respectively. The resultant mixtures were separately heated under reflux for 25 and 18 h, respectively. The reaction product in each case was worked up in the same manner as described earlier. The residues thus obtained were separately chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (30 : 1) eluate in the chromatography of the product obtained from **1g** gave **2c** (0.031 g) as a semisolid mass. Similar chromatography of the product obtained from **1h** also gave **2c** (0.034 g).

Chromatography of the acidic fraction obtained from I. paleacea: The petrol-EtOAc (80 : 1) eluate afforded **4a** as a viscous oil (0.04 g): ¹H NMR δ 2.84–2.93 (4H, m, H₂-α and H₂-α'), 3.76 (3H, s, ArOMe), 5.45 (1H, brs, ArOH), 6.32–6.35 (3H, m, H-3, H-4 and H-5) and 7.23–7.34 (5H, m, H-2', H-3', H-4', H-5' and H-6'); *m/z* (rel. int.) 228 (M⁺, 45), 137 (100), 91 (60). Acetylation of **4a** with Ac₂O and pyridine gave **4b** also as an oil: λ_{max} 221 and 270.5 nm (log ε 4.18 and 3.61); ν_{max} 1235 and 1760 (OAc), 1600, 1580, 1490, 1460, 1445, 895, 865, 835, 750, 725 and 704 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR δ 2.24 (3H, s, OAc), 2.85 (4H, s, H₂-α and H₂-α'), 3.76 (3H, s, ArOMe), 6.50 (1H, app.t, J₁ 1.8 and J₂ 2.1 Hz, H-4), 6.55 and 6.60 (each 1H broad signal, H-6 and H-2) and 7.18–7.32 (5H, m, H-2', H-3', H-4', H-5' and H-6').

Washing the column with petrol-EtOAc (30 : 1) gave **3a** (0.1 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 167°; [α]_D –33° (MeOH); ν_{max} 3110 (chelated OH), 1640 (chelated C=O), 1625, 1585, 825, 775 and 710 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR δ 12.18 (1H, s, chelated phenolic OH), 7.38–7.46 (5H, m, H-2', H-3', H-4', H-5' and H-6'), 6.13 (1H, s, H-8), 6.12 (1H, s, unchelated phenolic OH), 5.39 (1H, dd, J₁ 13.0 and J₂ 3.10 Hz, H-2), 3.93 (3H, s, ArOMe), 3.10 (1H, dd, J₁ 17.20 and J₂ 13.0 Hz, ax. H-3) and 2.82

(1H, dd, J₁ 17.20 and J₂ 3.10 Hz, equat. H-3). Acetylation of **3a** with Ac₂O and pyridine gave **3b** as a semisolid mass: λ_{max} 227, 257.5 and 326.5 nm (log ε 4.33, 4.12 and 3.88); ν_{max} 1225, 1760 and 1775 (OAc), 1685 (C=O), 1615, 1565, 765, 705 and 620 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR δ 2.24 and 2.34 (each 3H, s, 2 × OAc), 2.67 (1H, dd, J₁ 16.72 and J₂ 2.66 Hz, equat. H-3), 2.92 (1H, dd, J₁ 16.72 and J₂ 13.60 Hz, ax. H-3), 3.69 (3H, s, ArOMe), 5.38 (1H, dd, J₁ 13.60 and J₂ 2.66 Hz, H-2), 6.66 (1H, s, H-8) and 7.33 (5H, m, H-2', H-3', H-4', H-5' and H-6').

The petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate in the above chromatography afforded **3c** (0.05 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 226°; ν_{max} 3150 (chelated phenolic OH), 3340 (unchelated phenolic OH), 1650 (chelated C=O), 1620, 1605, 835, 820 and 685 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR δ 12.2 (1H, s, chelated phenolic OH), 7.33 (2H, d, J 8.6 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 6.88 (2H, d, J 8.6 Hz, H-3', H-5'), 6.47 (1H, s, unchelated phenolic OH), 6.11 (1H, s, H-8), 5.33 (1H, dd, J₁ 13.06 and J₂ 2.91 Hz, H-2), 4.99 (1H, s, unchelated phenolic OH), 3.94 (3H, s, ArOMe), 3.08 (1H, dd, J₁ 17.15 and J₂ 13.06 Hz, ax. H-3) and 2.78 (1H, dd, J₁ 17.15 and J₂ 2.91 Hz, equat. H-3). Acetylation of **3c** with Ac₂O and pyridine in the usual manner gave **3d** as amorph. powder: λ_{max} 222, 257.5 and 325.5 nm (log ε 4.31, 3.84 and 3.51); ν_{max} 1215 and 1770 (OAc), 1680 (C=O), 1617, 1570, 1530, 1505, 865, 845, 750, 690, 665 and 615 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR δ 2.30, 2.33 and 2.42 (each 3H, s, 3 × OAc), 2.76 (dd, J₁ 16.80 and J₂ 2.85 Hz, equat. H-3), 3.01 (dd, J₁ 16.80 and J₂ 13.68 Hz, ax. H-3), 3.77 (3H, s, ArOMe), 5.44 (1H, dd, J₁ 13.68 and J₂ 2.85 Hz, H-2), 6.74 (1H, s, H-8), 7.14 (2H, d, J 8.51 Hz, H-3', H-5') and 7.44 (2H, d, J 8.51 Hz, H-2', H-6').

Further washing the column with petrol-EtOAc (7 : 1) afforded gigantol (**4e**; 0.04 g) in the early fractions and batatasin-III (**4c**; 0.06 g) in the later fractions.

Chromatography of the neutral fraction obtained from *I. paleacea* yielded some uncharacterized oily mass.

Chromatography of the acidic fraction obtained from A. punctata: The petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate gave **4f** as a semisolid mass (0.03 g). Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (7 : 1) afforded **4g** (0.05 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 136°; λ_{max}^{EtOH-0.1M NaOH} 226, 244, 283.5 (sh) and 292 nm (sh) (log ε 4.07, 4.10, 3.57 and 3.48); ν_{max} 3400 (OH), 1610, 1580, 1514, 1414, 825, 815, 795, 775 and 650 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR δ 2.73 (4H, s, H₂-α and H₂-α'), 3.75 (6H, s, 2 × ArOMe), 5.36 (2H, br signal, 2 × OH), 6.27 (2H, s, H-2 and H-6), 6.68 (2H, d, J 8.5 Hz, H-3' and H-5') and 6.94 (2H, d, J 8.5 Hz, H-2' and H-6'); *m/z* (rel. int.) 274 [M⁺] (20), 167 (100) and 107 (71). **4g** was acetylated with Ac₂O and pyridine in the usual manner to give the corresponding diacetyl derivative **4h** as a semisolid mass (Found: C, 66.91; H, 6.10. C₂₀H₂₂O₆ re-

quires : C, 67.00; H, 6.19%); λ_{\max} 231 and 270.5 nm (log ϵ 4.26 and 3.60); ν_{\max} 1240 and 1765 (OAc), 1600, 1510, 1460, 815, 665, 645, 625 and 595 cm^{-1} (aromatic nucleus); $^1\text{H NMR}$ δ 2.19 and 2.23 (each 3H, s, 2 \times OAc), 2.79 (4H, ill-res. m, $\text{H}_2\text{-}\alpha$ and $\text{H}_2\text{-}\alpha'$), 3.68 (6H, s, 2 \times ArOMe), 6.28 (2H, s, H-2 and H-6), 6.90 and 7.07 (each 2H, d, J 8.4 Hz constituting an A_2B_2 system, H-3', H-5' and H-2', H-6'); m/z (rel. int.) 358 [M^+] (2), 316 (52), 274 (15), 168 (22), 167 (100), 107 (70) and 43 (77).

Chromatography of the neutral fraction obtained from *A. punctata* afforded only an uncharacterized oily mass.

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